

Green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens* Dist.) resistance ratings of rice varieties with different resistance genes, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Resistance gene ^a	Damage rating ^b					
		6 DI	7 DI	8 DI	9 DI	10 DI	11 DI
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 e	9.0 e	9.0 d	9.0 d
ASD 7	<i>Glh 2</i>	2.3 a	3.0 ab	5.0 bcd	5.7 cde	7.0 cd	7.7 d
IR8	<i>Glh 3</i>	1.7 a	3.7 b	5.0 bcd	6.3 de	7.0 cd	1.0 cd
Ptb 8	<i>glh 4</i>	1.0 a	2.3 ab	2.3 abc	3.0 abc	3.7 ab	3.1 ab
ASD 8	<i>Glh 5</i>	1.0 a	3.0 ab	3.7 abcd	5.0 bcd	5.7 bc	7.0 d
TAPL 196	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.7 a	1.7 ab	3.0 abcd	3.7 abcd	3.7 ab	5.0 bc
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.7 a	2.3 a
IR20	<i>Glh 3</i>	1.7 a	3.7 b	5.7 cde	6.3 de	7.7 cd	7.7 d
IR24	NA	2.3 a	3.7 b	5.7 cde	7.0 de	7.7 cd	7.7 d
IR26	NA	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.7 ab	2.3 ab	3.0 a	3.0 ab
IR36	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.7 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 a	1.7 a
IR42	NA	1.7 a	1.7 ab	2.3 abc	3.0 abc	3.0 a	3.0 ab
IR50	NA	1.0 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 a	1.7 a
IR54	NA	1.7 a	1.7 ab	3.0 abcd	2.3 ab	2.3 a	2.3 a
IR29 (resistant check)	NA	1.0 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	2.3 a	3.0 ab
TN1 (susceptible check)	—	5.0 b	6.3 c	7.0 de	8.3 e	8.3 d	9.0 d

^aNA = not ascertained. ^bScored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Within a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DI = days after infestation.

susceptible.

Genes *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, and *Glh 5* were identified at IRRI using a Philippine population of *N. virescens*

Genes *Glh 6* and *Glh 7* were identified in Bangladesh.

Pankhari 203, which is susceptible at Coimbatore, is highly resistant in the

Philippines. On the other hand, Moddai Karuppan is moderately susceptible in the Philippines but is highly resistant at Coimbatore and Bangladesh. ■

Resistance of rice cultivars and wild rices to thrips

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Among yield nursery seedlings of rice cultivars and wild rices screened for thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) resistance, Ptb 33, BG379-1, and Kalubalawee Sudurvi 305 were highly resistant. Gangala, Utri Rajappan, BG367-1, BG367-9, BG379-5, OB678, and IR17494-32-1-1-3-2 were resistant.

Wild rices found resistant to thrips at Coimbatore, India.

IRRI accession number	Name	Origin	Rating
103437	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	1
103443	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	1
103831	<i>O. sariva</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	1
103836	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	1
101171	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Tanzania	3
101510	<i>O. nivara</i>	India	3
101993	<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	3
103438	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	3
103791	<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Venezuela	3
103826	<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	3
103849	<i>O. perennis</i>	India	3

Eleven wild rices were resistant (see table). Varieties BG367-1, BG367-9, BG379-1, BG379-5, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, and OB678 also were resistant to brown planthopper. ■

Reaction of gall midge-resistant cultures at Warangal, India

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The Agricultural Research Station, Warangal, India, collaborated with the All India Cooperative Rice Improvement Project and IRRI in a study to identify gall midge biotypes and their distribution in India.

Field screening was conducted from 1977 to 1980. Observations on midge incidence were made on hill and tiller

Call midge biotype collaborative study, Warangal, India, and IRRI, 1978-80.

Culture	Hills infested (%)			Reaction ^a
	1978	1979	1980	
<i>Leuang 152</i>				
Leuang 152	0	0	0	R
CR95-JR-46-1	0	0	0	R
CR95-JR-214	0	14	0	MR
<i>Ptb</i>				
Ptb 10	0	— ^b	—	R
Ptb 18	0	0	4	R
Ptb 21	0	0	4	R
CR157-392-4	4	0	—	R
CR94-13	5	4	—	R
IR36	0	2	22	S
<i>Eswarakora</i>				
W1263	0	0	2	R
Kakatiya	0	0	0	R

(Continued on next page)

Table continued

Culture	Hills infested (%)			Reaction ^a
	1978	1979	1980	
WGL22585	—	—	2	R
IET2895/RP9-4	—	0	—	R
RD9	1	0	—	R
BKN6806-46-60	2	0	—	R
B1047d-Kn-1-2-2-3	18	33	—	S
<i>Muey Nahng 62 M</i>				
Muey Nahng 62 M	0	6	26	S
<i>Muey Nahng 62 M/Eswarakora</i>				
BKNBR1030-11-2	0	6	6	MR
Siam 29				
Siam 29	14	0	—	MR
Siam 29 (ACC5915)	—	—	37	S
Siam 29 (ACC5473)	—	—	45	S
Siam 29 (ACC5916)	—	—	32	S
Siam 29 (ACC42)	—	—	18	S
Siam 29 (ACC36665)	—	—	32	S
RP6-17	0	0	0	R
W6L13400	0	0	0	R
CR189-4	2	0	—	R
OB677				
OB677	0	0	0	R
75-159	0	0	—	R
BG401-2	—	—	0	R
<i>Ptb/Siam 29</i>				
IR4744-123-1-3	3	11	—	MR
IR8 (susceptible check)	26	12	—	S
Jaya (susceptible check)	—	25	21	S
Tella hamsa (susceptible check)	—	—	44	S

^aBased on highest infestation over 3-year period. Resistant (R) = 0-5%; moderately resistant (MR) = 6-15%; susceptible (S) = 16% or more. ^bNo data available.

basis at 30 and 50 days after transplanting. The data represent the highest replications (see table).

Accessions of Siam 29, a prominent donor for many resistant cultures, were susceptible to gall midge. Its derivatives

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WGL13400 (Surekha) and RP6-17 (Phalguna) were resistant and are popular varieties in the region. Eswarakora derivatives W1263 and Kakatiya, originated at Warangal, were resistant while the exotic B1047d-kn-1-2-2-3 (Pelita 1/Eswarakora) was susceptible. Leuang 152 and OB677 were resistant. Leuang 152 derivatives reacted differently. CR95-JR-46-1 was resistant, while CR95-JR-214 was moderately resistant. Muey Nahng 62 M was susceptible. All Ptb derivatives except IR36 were resistant. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Productive nodal panicles after severe water stress

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The production of a second or nodal panicle from the primary tiller after water stress at the flowering period has been observed in rice. IR7790-18-1-2 produced a second panicle from the penultimate node of the main culm after a 10-day drought at the onset of flowering of the primary panicle (Fig. 1). The nodal panicles flowered about 60 days after partial or total desiccation of the primary panicles. Side tillers also flow-

1. Second nodal flowering pattern in rice after drought, IIRRI.